

Studies in the Rearrangement of Spiranes: Part V: Synthesis of 1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydrospiro[2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] and its 7'-Methyl Derivative and their Rearrangement on Catalytic Dehydrogenation

D. N. CHATTERJEE* and S. R. CHAKRABORTY

Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta-700012.

Manuscript received 22 November 1975; accepted 12 March 1976

The synthesis of 1', 2', 3', 4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1, 2'-naphthalene] (I; R = H) and its 7'-methyl derivative (I; R = CH₃) have been carried out with a view to studying the mode of fission of the substituted cyclopentane ring on catalytic dehydrogenation. When heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst, they underwent smooth rearrangement yielding 1-*n*-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene and 1-*n*-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene respectively, the structures of which have been confirmed by authentic syntheses. The spiranes have been prepared starting from the anhydride of 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid, benzene and toluene by an extension of the method developed earlier¹.

IN our previous communications, we reported the synthesis of different spiranes derived from the anhydride of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid¹ and 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid² by their condensation with benzene, toluene. When heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst, they all underwent smooth rearrangement yielding alkylated phenanthrene derivatives without any loss of carbon atom. Our previous studies on the subject revealed that the fission of the substituted cyclopentane ring always took place away from the substitution. The resulting chain on angular cyclisation and dehydrogenation yielded the desired hydrocarbons. In order to study the effect of more bulky groups on the mode of ring fission, the synthesis of 1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] and its 7'-methyl derivative have been undertaken in the present work. When heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst, both the spiranes were found to undergo smooth rearrangement by fission of the substituted cyclopentane ring in an identical manner giving 1-*n*-propyl-2-methyl- and 1-*n*-propyl 2,6-di-methylphenanthrene.

Our observation on the mode of ring fission was somewhat a departure from that of Chatterjee⁵ who studied the rearrangement of 1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-*n*-propylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] and the corresponding 2-*n*-butyl derivative under condition of catalytic dehydrogenation and isolated 1-methyl- and 1-ethyl pyrene respectively. The result was interpreted as going through fission of the substituted cyclopentane ring adjacent to substitution

followed by simultaneous double ring closure of the resulting chain by cyclodehydrogenation giving ultimately a pyrene derivative. Thus it appears that substitution of one additional methyl group in the 3-position of the cyclopentane ring causes the ring fission to occur in a reverse manner leading to the formation of an alkylated phenanthrene rather than a pyrene derivative and the same explanation¹ about the mode of ring fission seems plausible.

The starting material for the synthesis of the above spiranes, 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II) was prepared by the condensation of 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentanone with ethyl cyanoacetate followed by addition of KCN and hydrolysis. 2-*n*-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentanone had been prepared by the condensation between ethyl laevulinate and *n*-butyl magnesium bromide followed by PPA cyclisation and catalytic hydrogenation according to the general procedure described earlier^{1,4}.

The AlCl₃ catalysed condensation of the anhydride of (II) with benzene gave α -(2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (III, R = H) in 80% yield. The keto-acid on catalytic reduction in a Paar apparatus gave a good yield of α -(2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- γ -phenylbutyric acid which on PPA cyclisation afforded 3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane - 1,2'-[(1'(H) naphthalen]-1'-one (IV; R = H) in 67% yield. The spiroketone which did not form a 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative due to steric hindrance³ was catalytically reduced in a Paar apparatus in excellent yield to 1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I; R = H). The spirane on catalytic dehydrogenation underwent smooth

* Senior author.

rearrangement giving 1-*n*-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene as the exclusive product, the structure of which was confirmed by an independent synthesis by an extension of the method due to Bardhan and Nasipuri⁶. Methyl ester of γ -(2-carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-butyric acid⁶ on Dieckmann cyclisation with powdered sodium methoxide in dry benzene followed by alkylation with methyl iodide gave 1-keto-2-methyl-2-carbomethoxy-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (V; R = H) which on hydrolysis with a mixture of acetic acid and hydrochloric acid gave 1-keto-2-methyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (VI; R = H) in good yield. This tricyclic ketone on Grignard reaction with *n*-propylmagnesium bromide followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation gave 1-*n*-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene.

Our findings on the rearrangement of the spirane (I, R = CH₃), prepared in an identical route starting from the anhydride of II and toluene, was similar. When heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst, it gave 1-*n*-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene as the sole product, the structure of which has been confirmed by an unambiguous synthesis starting from 1-keto-2,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene² (VI; R = CH₃) and *n*-propylmagnesium bromide. No anthracene or pyrene derivatives could be isolated from the products of dehydrogenation of the spiranes.

Experimental

All m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. U.V. spectra were recorded in 95% ethanol in a Unicam Spectrophotometer, Model SP 500. I.R. spectra were recorded in Unicam Spectrophotometer, Model SP 200G. Pet. ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60°–80°.

2-*n*-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentanone

γ -Methyl- γ -*n*-butyl butyrolactone (17 g) prepared from *n*-butylmagnesium bromide and ethyl laevulinate was heated with PPA (200 g) in an oil bath at 120°–125° with stirring for 2.5 hr. The resulting dark red complex was decomposed with crushed ice and worked up in the usual way to give 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopent-2-ene-1-one (12.5 g) which was hydrogenated in ethanol in the presence of 10% Pd-C catalyst. Usual work up as described in the case of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentanone¹ afforded 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentanone as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 190°, *n*_D²⁰ 1.4380 (Found: C, 77.32; H, 11.32%. Calc. for C₉H₁₆O: C, 77.14; H, 11.43%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in fine red needles, m.p. 124° (Found: N, 17.37%. Calc. for C₁₅H₂₀N₄O₄: N, 17.50%). The semicarbazone crystallised from dil. ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 182°–183°, (Found: N, 21.14%. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₉N₃O: N, 21.32%).

2-*n*-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II)

A mixture of the foregoing ketone (20 g), ethylcyanoacetate (22 g), acetic acid (8 ml), ammonium acetate (4 g) and dry toluene (100 ml) was heated under reflux in an oil bath in a Cope's apparatus at 130°–150° for 6 hr and then at 150°–170° for 10 hr. Usual work up gave the unsaturated cyano-ester (27 g) as a colourless thick liquid, b.p. 133°–135°/1 mm, *n*_D²⁰ 1.4800. (Found: N, 6.13%. Calc. for C₁₄H₂₁NO₂: N, 5.96%).

A solution of potassium cyanide (27 g) in 54 ml. water was added to the foregoing unsaturated cyano-ester (38 g) dissolved in rectified spirit (150 ml). The solution was left for 7 days. Usual work up followed by careful fractionation afforded the di-cyanoester (23 g) boiling at 133°–135°/0.5 mm, which on hydrolysis according to the procedure described earlier¹ gave 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II) in 92% yield. The acid crystallised from acetic acid in colourless plates, m.p. 141° (Found: C, 63.33; H, 8.92%. Calc. for C₁₂H₂₀O₄: C, 63.16; H, 8.77%).

The *anilic acid*, prepared by heating the anhydride of the aforesaid acid (II) with aniline in benzene, was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 150° (Found: C, 70.65; H, 8.03%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₅NO₃: C, 71.28; H, 8.25%).

α -(2-*n*-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- β -benzoyl propionic acid (III; R = H)

Condensation of the anhydride of 2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (5.25 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ (7.34 g) as described earlier¹ gave the keto-acid (6 g) which on further crystallisation from ethanol afforded the pure acid (III; R = H) as stout plates, m.p. 113°. (Found: C, 74.55; H, 8.69%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₄O₃: C, 75.00; H, 8.33%). 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 228°–229° (decom.). (Found: N, 11.68%. Calc. for C₂₄H₂₃N₄O₆: N, 11.96%).

α -(2-*n*-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- γ -phenyl butyric acid

The foregoing keto-acid (III; R = H) (5 g) was reduced with hydrogen in 40 ml. of ethanol containing 0.5 g. of 10% Pd-C catalyst in a Paar apparatus according to the procedure described earlier¹ to give α -(2-*n*-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- γ -phenyl butyric acid (4.6 g) as a thick liquid which solidified on cooling and crystallised from pet-ether in colourless needles, m.p. 79°–80° (Found: C, 78.72; H, 9.58%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₆O₂: C, 78.83; H, 9.49%).

3',4'-Dihydrospiro [2-n-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1, 2'(1'H)-naphthalene]-1'-one (IV; R = H).

The foregoing butyric acid derivative (3.5 g) was cyclised by stirring with PPA (60 g) on a steam bath for 0.5 hr when a deep orange colour was developed. Usual work up followed by distillation gave the spiro-ketone (IV; R = H) as a colourless liquid, b.p. 165°–166°/1 mm., n_D^{30} 1.5450. (Found: C, 83.95; H, 9.13%. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{24}O$: C, 84.37; H, 9.37%). The ketone did not form the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative⁸ but showed a strong I.R. carbonyl absorption band at 5.95 μ and U.V. absorptions λ_{max} at 232 nm (log ϵ 3.92), 249 nm (log ϵ 3.98), 298 nm (log ϵ 3.16), characteristic of a conjugated cyclic ketone^{8(a)}.

1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydrospiro [2-n-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I; R = H)

The foregoing spiro-ketone (IV; R = H) (1.2 g) was reduced with hydrogen in ethanol (25 ml) containing 0.1 g of 10% Pd-C catalyst under a pressure of 40 lbs/sq. in at 45°. The solution was filtered and distilled under reduced pressure when the spirane (I; R = H) (0.8 g) was obtained as mobile liquid, b.p. 145°–150°/1 mm. (Found: C, 88.37; H, 10.34%. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{28}$: C, 89.25; H, 10.75%).

Clemmensen reduction of the spiroketone (IV; R = H) led to the formation of a highly viscous liquid which slowly solidified and melted at 120°–121°. It showed an intense hydroxylic. I.R. peak at 3 μ and is believed to be a pinacol formed by the bimolecular reduction of the spiroketone.

Dehydrogenation of spirane (I; R = H): Isolation of 1-n-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene

A mixture of the spirane (I; R = H) (0.5 g) and 10% Pd-C catalyst (50 mg) was heated in a metal bath at 320°–330° for 3 hrs and then at 330°–350° for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was extracted with benzene, chromatographed over alumina and sublimed under reduced pressure. The sublimate (0.1 g) was converted into picrate in methanol. The separated picrate after crystallisation from methanol was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 123°. The mixed m.p. with the picrate of an authentic sample of 1-n-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene was not depressed.

The hydrocarbon, generated from the picrate, crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 69° and was identified as 1-n-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene by comparison with an authentic synthetic specimen.

Synthesis of 1-n-propyl-2-methylphenanthrene**1-Keto-2-methyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (VI; R = H)**

γ (2-carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-butyric acid (4 g), prepared according to Bardhan and Nasipuri⁶, was esterified by an ethereal solution of diazomethane. The methyl ester, b.p. 192°–194°/2 mm. (4 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added to a suspension of powdered sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (0.5 g) and absolute methanol (5 ml), in 25 ml. of dry benzene. The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere

on a steam bath for 2 hr when a semisolid mass was obtained. Refluxing was continued for another 2 hr. The mass was then cooled in ice and 10 ml. of methyl iodide was added. The mixture was left overnight and then refluxed for 2 hr. The solution was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and worked up in the usual way. Distillation afforded 2.7 g. of 1-keto-2-carbomethoxy-2-methyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (V; R = H) as a thick oil, b.p. 197°–200°/1.5 mm, which was boiled under reflux with conc. hydrochloric acid (30 ml), acetic acid (60 ml) and water (5 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere for 2 hr. Usual work up followed by distillation afforded the ketone (VI; R = H) (2.0 g) as a thick oil, b.p. 160°–165°/1 mm, which after chromatographic purification over alumina in pet-ether slowly solidified. It crystallised from pet-ether in fine needles, m.p. 51°–52°. (Found: C, 84.72; H, 7.51%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O$: C, 84.90; H, 7.55%). It showed U.V. absorption λ_{max} 230 nm (log ϵ 4.0087), 236 nm (log ϵ 4.0143), 253 nm (log ϵ 3.6354) and 298 nm (log ϵ 4.0764), characteristic of a conjugated cyclic ketone.

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ethanol as red plates, m.p. 212° (Found: N, 14.15%. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{20}N_4O_4$: N, 14.28%). The semicarbazone crystallised from aqueous ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 226°–227°. (Found: N, 15.24%. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{18}N_3O$: N, 15.61%).

1-n-Propyl-2-methylphenanthrene

A solution of the foregoing ketone (VI; R = H) (0.5 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added at room temperature to a well stirred solution of *n*-propylmagnesium bromide, prepared from magnesium (0.2 g), *n*-propyl bromide (5 ml) and dry ether (30 ml). The solution was left overnight and then refluxed for 2 hr. Usual work up and sublimation gave 0.4 g. of semisolid mass which was heated with 60 mg. of 10% Pd-C catalyst at 300°–320° for half an hr. The mass was extracted with benzene, purified by chromatography over alumina and then sublimed. The sublimate (0.2 g) was converted into picrate. The separated picrate crystallised from methanol in fine orange needles, m.p. 123° (Found: N, 8.78%). Calc. for $C_{24}H_{21}N_3O_7$: N, 9.07%).

The hydrocarbon, regenerated from the picrate, crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 69° (Found: C, 92.14; H, 7.52%. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}$: C, 92.31; H, 7.69%). It showed U.V. absorption λ_{max} 258 nm (log ϵ 4.7272), 281 nm (log ϵ 4.0127), 289 nm (log ϵ 3.8851), 302 nm (log ϵ 4.0047), 320 nm (log ϵ 2.5091), 336 nm (log ϵ 2.6048) and 352 nm (log ϵ 2.4307), characteristic of a substituted phenanthrene^{8(b)}.

The sym-trinitrobenzene complex crystallised from ethanol in fine orange yellow needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: N, 9.69%. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{21}N_3O_6$: N, 9.39%).

 $\alpha\alpha$ -(2-n-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- β -(*p*-tolyl)-propionic acid (III; R = CH₃)

The anhydride of 2-n-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (5.25 g) was condensed with

toluene in the presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 (7.34 g) as described before to give 5 g. of the keto-acid (III; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) which crystallised from glacial acetic acid as compact plates, m.p. $130^\circ\text{--}131^\circ$ (Found: C, 75.34; H, 8.48%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.49; H, 8.61%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a mixture of benzene and ethanol in orange-yellow needles, m.p. $214^\circ\text{--}215^\circ$ (Found: N, 11.43%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$: N, 11.62%). Oxidation of the keto-acid (III; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) by sodium hypobromite solution gave *p*-toluic acid, m.p. 181° .

*α -(2-n-Propyl-3-methylcyclopentane)- γ -(*p*-tolyl)-butyric acid*

The foregoing keto-acid (III; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) (4.5 g) was reduced with hydrogen using 10% Pd-C catalyst in a Paar apparatus to give the reduced acid (4 g) as a thick oil which solidified on trituration with pet-ether. It crystallised from pet-ether in colourless needles, m.p. $102^\circ\text{--}103^\circ$. (Found: C, 78.84; H, 9.83%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$: C, 79.16; H, 9.72%).

7'-Methyl-3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-n-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'H)-naphthalen]-1'-one (IV; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$)

The preceding reduced acid (3 g) was cyclised by stirring with PPA (40 g) on a steam bath for 0.5 hr. when a deep orange colour was developed. Usual work up followed by chromatography over alumina in benzene solution and distillation under reduced pressure gave the spiroketone (IV; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) (2 g) as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. $160^\circ\text{--}165^\circ/0.5$ mm, $n_D^{25} 1.5375$. (Found: C, 88.34; H, 9.37%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 9.63%). The ketone did not form 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative³ but showed a strong I.R. carbonyl absorption band at 5.95μ and U.V. absorption λ_{max} 234 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.846), 250 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0565) and 300 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.2950), characteristics of a conjugated cyclic ketone^{3(a)}.

7'-Methyl-1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydrospiro [2-n-propyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$)

One gram of the foregoing ketone (IV; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) was reduced with hydrogen in a Paar apparatus at 40 lbs/sq. inch. pressure at 55° in the presence of 10% Pd-C catalyst in ethanol (10 ml). Filtration followed by careful fractionation afforded the spirane (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) (0.7 g) as a mobile liquid, b.p. $150^\circ\text{--}153^\circ/1$ mm. (Found: C, 88.78; H, 10.72%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}$: C, 89.06; H, 10.94%).

Dehydrogenation of the spirane (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$): Isolation of 1-n-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene

Dehydrogenation of 0.5 of the above spirane (I; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) in the presence of 10% Pd-C catalyst (50 mg) as described in the case of the spirane (I; $\text{R} = \text{H}$) gave 0.1 g of a thick liquid which was converted into the picrate in methanol. The picrate was crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. $148^\circ\text{--}149^\circ$, not depressed on admixture with the picrate of 1-*n*-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene obtained from an unambiguous synthesis.

The hydrocarbon, regenerated from the picrate, crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. $102^\circ\text{--}103^\circ$. It was identified as 1-*n*-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene by comparison with an authentic synthetic specimen.

Synthesis of 1-n-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene

A solution of 1-keto-2,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene³ (VI; $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) (0.5 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added slowly to a stirred solution of *n*-propyl-magnesiumbromide, prepared from magnesium (0.2 g), *n*-propylbromide (5 ml) and dry ether (30 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hr. and then decomposed with cold dil. sulphuric acid. Usual work up followed by sublimation afforded 0.45 g of a semisolid mass which was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (50 mg) at $300^\circ\text{--}320^\circ$ for half an hour. Extraction followed by chromatography over alumina in benzene and sublimation afforded 0.2 g of a solid mass. Repeated crystallisation from ethanol gave 0.1 g of pure 1-*n*-propyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene as fine needles, m.p. $102^\circ\text{--}103^\circ$. (Found: C, 91.78; H, 8.18%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}$: C, 91.93; H, 8.07%). It showed U.V. absorption at 260 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.6955), 282 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.5578), 292 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.8652), 304 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0173), 322 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.5578), 338 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.7048) and 354 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.656), characteristic of a substituted phenanthrene^{3(b)}.

The picrate of the above hydrocarbon crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. $148^\circ\text{--}149^\circ$. (Found: N, 8.94%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$: N, 8.80%).

The *sym*-trinitrobenzene complex crystallised from ethanol in fine orange needles, m.p. 167° (Found: N, 8.98%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$: N, 9.11%).

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Prof. (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee of the University College of Science for help in the micro-analysis of some of the samples and to Dr. B. Pathak of the Applied Chemistry Department for pressure hydrogenation. Financial assistance from the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi and Government of West Bengal is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. D. N. CHATTERJEE and S. R. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 507.
2. Part IV of this series, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (communicated).
3. W. COCKER *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1781.
4. D. VARECH, *Bull. Soc. Chem. (France)*, 1965, 1666.
5. D. N. CHATTERJEE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 414, 5131.
6. J. C. BARDHAN and D. NASIFURI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 350.
7. S. DEV and RAI, *Experientia*, 1955, 11, 114.
8. R. A. FRIEDEL and M. ORCHIN, "Ultraviolet Spectra of Aromatic Hydrocarbons", John Wiley and Sons, New York, N. Y., 1951 (a) Chart 59, 60, 61, (b) Chart 357, 345.